

Teacher's Motivation & Job Satisfaction

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Abstract -Teacher motivation is an important concern for educational leaders and managers because teacher motivation has an important effect on student motivation. Teacher Motivation is also important for advance of educational reforms. Job satisfaction which simply define, at this point as the difference between the amounts of rewards works receive and the amount they believe they should receive. The purpose of this study is to explore the factors that influence teacher's motivation & Job satisfaction. Teachers are more arguably the most important group of professionals for our nation's future. The method used for data collection include questionnaires and interviews from teachers of Forty-five Govt. high Schools, inter college, and fifteen Private schools & Inter college of Kotli District (AJK). We have review of the literature maximum articles related to foreign countries. During this research paper one thing strikes me; the major factor influences job satisfaction is political pressure. This factor has not seen prominent in foreign countries. Other major problem in colleges and school is negligence of merit which is the main effect on proper education; the intelligent candidates are neglected due to political influence. The paper sought to describe various techniques, which help in teaching motivation & job satisfaction.

Keyword- Teacher Teacher's Motivation & Job Satisfaction in Azad Jammu and Kashmir.

Introduction

Motivation has been one of the most frequently-researched subjects in the fields of psychology and education. Therefore, it is only natural to define motivation as a force, one that makes us constantly move, act or do things. "Motivation is defined as some kind of internal drive which pushes someone to do things in order to achieve something" (Harmer, 2001, p.98). In an

organization, motivation can be defined as a glue that holds things together. In addition, Robbins (1989, p.168) defined motivation as “the willingness to exert high levels of effort toward organizational goals, conditioned by the effort’s ability to satisfy some individual need”.

Job satisfaction

Job satisfaction which is closely linked with motivation is defined by Schaffer (1953, p.3) as being one of individuals’ needs fulfilments: “Overall job satisfaction will vary directly with the extent to which those needs of an individual which can be satisfied in a job are actually satisfied”. However, others have also put forward views on job satisfaction such as Lawler (1973) who focuses on expectations rather than needs.

Ryan and Deci (2000: 71) define the extrinsic motivation is concerned with the performance of an activity to succeed in getting separable outcomes, which contrasts sharply with intrinsic motivation. According to Hawley (1985:58), in order to increase teacher competence career ladder plans should be done. There are some principles to be designed for career ladder plans.

These are:

- For high performance, economic rewards are important.
- In order to keep higher levels of pay and status, teachers carry on showing high performance.
- There should not be any competitive rewards, which can discourage peer interaction and social approval important to effective teaching.
- Fair and predictable assessment measures should be used.

Akehurst, Comeche, & Galindo,(2009). found that if the employees find their job fulfilling and rewarding, they tend to be more satisfied with their jobs. Employees’s satisfaction is generally regarded as an important ingredient for organisational success. According to several authorities the proper approach to work motivation on lies in a careful distinction between extrinsic and intrinsic rewards. Herzberg (1964) distinguishes between extrinsic rewards surrounding a job (such as salaries, fringe benefits and job security) and intrinsic rewards of job itself (such as self respect, sense of accomplishment and personal growth). Intrinsic rewards, according to Herzberg is more satisfying and motivating. Recent studies have shown fairly conclusively that teachers

are motivated by extrinsic rewards. Through this research paper I found that teachers are motivated by many factors such as Salary, Skill development, working environment etc. This research has been done in Kotli (A.k), through questionnaires and interview.

Literature Review

Teachers are primarily motivated by Intrinsic & Extrinsic rewards (Maslow). (1964) Distinguishes between extrinsic rewards surrounding a job (such as salaries, firing benefits, & job security) and intrinsic rewards of job itself (such as self –respect, sense of accomplishment, & personal growth). Recent studies have shown fairly conclusively that teachers are motivated more by intrinsic than by extrinsic rewards. Davis Joan & M. Sandra (July / August 2000), they describe that the purpose of our study was to examine how principals' empowering behaviors that focuses on intrinsic empowerment relate to intrinsic empowerment, job satisfaction & job stress. K Jane Seal (2000) he focuses on three assessments emerged as the most developed an invalidated three- page questionnaire, which was distributed to students in the middle of their final year of study. Factors associated with the assessments which may influence student motivation, four factors associated with assessment influence on student motivation: 1 Perceived relevance of the assessment; 2 Assessment content; 3 Enthusiastic lecturers; 4 Group influence. Shyan Hong. Jeou (July 2005), he says that the basic purpose of this study is to explore the factors that influence creative teaching & find out what effective strategies are used. The research is qualitative rather than quantitative. Activities are subject to several factors: teachers' personalities, family backgrounds, learning process, life experiences, education beliefs, diligence & motivation. These factors may exercise different influences from person to person, but are closely related & mutually affect. Herzberg (1964) distinguishes between extrinsic rewards surrounding a Job (such as salaries, fringe benefits & Job security) and intrinsic rewards of Job itself (such as self-respect, sense of accomplishment and personal growth). Intrinsic rewards, according to Herzberg are more satisfying and motivating. Eskandari ,(2010) research that, there is no significant relationship between job satisfaction and variable such as the nature of the work, manager's supervisory style, colleague's behavior in the workplace. Hosseini, (2008) variable such as Age, work experience, educational level and income have been effective in motivating the employees. Oiolube (2006), the relevance of job satisfaction and motivation are very crucial to the long-term growth of any educational system around the world. While every teacher constantly agitates for the job satisfaction and demand for better conditions of service are beyond

the resources of the government. Raj. Kamla (2011), find that teachers are motivated through improving on their salaries, working conditions and providing them resources.

Methodology

I developed questionnaire, which was distributed to teachers and also conducted interview. Data was collected through sample survey, teachers were randomly selected. Teachers were master of English, Physics, Chemistry, Bio, M.B.A, M.P.A, and Islamic Study etc. highly qualified teachers with related to high school, inter college, Postgraduate College, Govt sectors as well as private sectors. The teachers in the sample represent a moderately accurate cross-section of the school. 67% Male teachers, 33% Female teachers from which 50% Male teachers in "Govt" sectors and 16% Male teachers from private sectors. 16% Female teachers from "Govt" sectors and 16% Female teacher from private sector

Measure

The questionnaire consisted of three parts. First step related to motivation factors, second to job satisfaction. The last and third part was designed to determine how the respondents give suggestion about satisfaction. In this section seven questions were asked to the respondents, such as how much should be salary, incentives, promotion, boss, training etc. Further data divided in to age group. First age group is below to 30, second age group is 31 to 45 and third age group is 45 to 60.

Results of Age Group below to 30

The results show that this age group is entirely dissatisfied with salary, promotion, policies, pensions and political pressures. Political pressure is a major factor which highly affected by this age group. Through interview I know that the respondent of this age group are highly qualified but not satisfied with their job especially private sector respondent are completely dissatisfied due to "job security" and "salary". This age group is 64% dissatisfied with salary and 68% dissatisfied with promotion, 68% policies of department 68% with pension and 72% with political pressure. Highly affected by political pressure. This age group is highly satisfied with

“colleagues” and boss. High level of satisfaction with “colleagues” shows that this age group is very social.

Descriptive Statistics Age Group Below to 30

Variables	No.	yes	No	Mean
Salary	25	9	16	1.6400
Incentive	25	17	8	1.3200
Promotion	25	8	17	1.6800
Boss	25	15	10	1.4000
Colleagues	25	22	3	1.1200
Skilldevelopment	25	12	13	1.5200
Policies	25	8	17	1.7083
Environment	25	12	13	1.5200
Pension	25	8	17	1.7083
Political pressure	25	6	18	1.8000

Result of Age Group 31to 45

This age group is also dissatisfied with salary, incentives, promotion, policies of organization, political pressure. This age group is also highly affected by political pressure, the major problem of this age group is negligence of merit which is the main effect on proper education the intelligent candidates are neglected. There is a little bit difference between age group “below to 30” and 31to 45.the major difference between two age group in “environment” age group below to 30 is 48% satisfied with “environment” and age group 31to 45 is 81% satisfied with “environment” this difference shows that with the passage of time the employees adjusted themselves with “environment”.36.4% peoples are satisfied with “salary” 31.8% with “incentives” and 22.7% are satisfied. High level of satisfaction of this age group with two factors 95.5% peoples are satisfied with “colleagues”& 81.8% peoples are satisfied with “boss”. Just like to age group below to 30, high level of satisfaction of this age group with colleagues that is 95.5%. high level of dissatisfactions of this age group with “promotion criteria” that is 77.3 people are dissatisfied with promotion criteria, promotion criteria is very low.

Descriptive Statistics

Age Group 31 to 45

Variables	No.	Yes	No.	Mean
Salary	22	8	14	1.6364
Incentive	22	7	15	1.6818
Promotioncriteria	22	5	17	1.7727

Boss	22	18	4	1.5455
Colleagues	22	21	1	1.0455
Skilldevelopment	22	13	9	1.4091
Policies	22	5	17	1.7727
Environment	22	18	4	1.1818
Pension	22	8	14	1.6364
Politicalpressure	22	5	17	1.7727

Result of Age Group 46 to 60

The results of this age group are different from upper and middle class. 57.1% respondents are satisfied from “salary” “skill development” policy” “political pressure” level of satisfaction about four factors is same that is 57.1%. This age group is dissatisfied from “incentive, promotion pension”. Through direct discussion to this age group I known that this group faced a lots of problems such as large size of classes, lack of subject specialist, buildings and furniture is not available in rural areas. I see that in high schools the teachers appointed are not related to the subject, this age group faced major problems of subject specialist.

Descriptive Statistics

Age Group 46to60

Variables	No.	Yes	No	Mean
Salary	14	8	6	1.4286
Incentive	14	4	10	1.7143
Promotioncriteria	14	4	10	1.7143
Boss	14	9	5	1.3571
Colleagues	14	11	3	1.2143
Skilldevelopment	14	8	6	1.4286
Policies	14	8	6	1.4286
Environment	14	10	4	1.2857
Pension	14	5	9	1.6429
Politicalpressure	14	6	8	1.7429

Conclusion

Lack of motivation may cause teachers to be less successful in teaching. Through this research paper I concluded that every teacher is not motivated entirely by the same demands and needs job satisfaction of each employee is different from there. Some factors such as “income, salary, and promotion criteria” all teachers are entirely dissatisfied. During this research paper one thing strikes me is that “political pressure political pressure should be reduced. Recruitment should be on the basis of merit. Since teacher reported that they were involved excited and happy during successful class room discussion it would be appear that reduction in class size would help promote job satisfaction. Another thing I concluded through discussion with teachers is that there is lack of subject specialist, in high schools the teachers appointed are not related to the subject teachers are not related to the subject. Teacher’s especially younger ones also reported that they were not satisfied with their income and highly affected by political pressure. There is negligence of merit which is the main effect on proper education the intelligent candidates are neglected due to political pressure. An other thing found during research is that check and balance system of government is not effective, there should be need an effective check and balance system. If there are not any factors motivating teachers then productivity will decrease dramatically. I come to the conclusion that all the political pressure should be furnished. Salaries should be increased and proper training should be given to the teachers with the passage of time so that they may properly teach the students. A committee of honest people should be set up to appoint the teachers. Through personal survey, an other important thing concluded that ‘Evaluation system help to motivate teachers.’ An evaluation system, if well signed provides teachers with the necessary feedback to assess their own professional growth. A poorly designed evaluation system can be disastrous, pitting teachers against administrators. Administrators should encourage teachers to take part in the design and implementation of practical, research based evaluation system customized to individual district needs. The main purpose of evaluation should be to provide information to help teachers improve their teaching performance.

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